

THE REDUCED SMARANDACHE CUBE-PARTIAL-DIGITAL SUBSEQUENCE IS INFINITE

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Abstract . In this paper we prove that the reduced Smarandache cube-partial-digital subsequence is infinite.

Key words . reduced Smarandache cube-partial-digital subsequence , infinite.

From all cube integers $0, 1, 8, 27, 64, 125, \dots$, we choose only the terms can be partitioned into groups of digits which are also perfect cubes and disregarding the cube numbers of the form $N \cdot 10^{3t}$, where N is also a cube number and t is a positive integer . Such sequence is called the reduced Smarandache cube-partial-digital subsequence . Bencze [1] and Smith [2] independently proposed the following question.

Question . How many terms in the reduced Smarandache cube-partial-digital subsequence?

In this paper we completely solve the mentioned question . We prove the following result.

Theorem . The reduced Smarandache cube-partial-digital subsequence has infinitely many terms.

Proof . For any positive integer n with $n > 1$, let

$$(1) \quad B(n) = 3 \cdot 10^n + 3.$$

Then we have

$$(2) \quad \begin{aligned} B(n)^3 &= 27 \cdot 10^{3n} + 81 \cdot 10^{2n} + 81 \cdot 10^n + 27 \\ &= 27 \underbrace{0 \dots 0}_{(n-2)\text{zeros}} 81 \underbrace{0 \dots 0}_{(n-2)\text{zeros}} 81 \underbrace{0 \dots 0}_{(n-2)\text{zeros}} 27. \end{aligned}$$

By (1) and (2) , we see that $(B(n))^3$ belongs to the reduced Smarandache cube-partial-digital subsequence . Thus , this sequence is infinite . The theorem is proved.

References

- [1] M. Bencze , Smarandache relationships and subsequence , Smarandache Notions J. 11(2000), 79-85.
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